

spikelet sterility near that of CSR6. In 1983, the trial was repeated with nine genotypes and check varieties CSR1, CSR3, and CSR6. In situ soil salinity ranged from 4.5 to 5.4 dS/m at flowering. Panicle length of Panionla (28.0 cm) was significantly high but similar to that of

Chakra kunda (27.2 cm) and CSR6 (27.7 cm). Rhas Panjara produced the most (141) spikelets/panicle, followed by Chakra kunda (139), Panionla (133), Patini (131), and CSR6 (113). Spikelet sterility was lowest for Velki (12.8%), Valuki (13.1%), CSR1 (14.7%), and

CSR6 (15.9%) and maximum for Panionla (35.8%).

Although Valuki yielded highest (3.4 t/ha), it was similar to Velki (3.4 t/ha) and CSR6 (3.2 t/ha), indicating their suitability for cultivation in rainfed, coastal saline fields. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DEEP WATER

Performance of some rice plant types under two water depths

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We sought to identify suitable rice varieties and lines for double- and single-cropped lowlands in Kolleru. Flooding occurs annually and rice must tolerate 30- to 100-cm water depths.

Growth duration and plant height of 10 tall and short varieties and lines were evaluated at 5- (control) and 60-cm water depths in 1983 kharif. Plots were flooded 40 d after transplanting and water depth was maintained for 75 d.

At 60-cm depth, plant height increased from 8 to 36 cm over the control, depending on variety. Grain yield was 1.0

Grain yield and characters of rice varieties for deep water areas, 1983 kharif, Pulla, Andhra Pradesh, India.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	Flowering duration (d)			Plant ht (cm)		
		60 cm	5 cm	Increase over control (%)	60 cm	5 cm	increase over control (%)
PLA1100	2.3	152	135	17	138	110	28
IET6314	1.9	134	124	10	149	113	36
MTU5293	1.9	135	132	3	133	119	14
IET5656	2.0	135	131	4	150	124	26
Pankaj	1.9	145	133	12	148	130	18
CN540	1.9	130	121	9	164	142	22
NC492	2.2	139	130	9	182	174	8
Swarna	1.5	131	123	8	139	109	30
MTU7633	1.3	131	127	4	134	106	28
IR42	1.0	131	115	16	118	108	10

to 2.3 t/ha at 60 cm and 4.0 to 6.0 t/ha in the 5-cm plots (see table). Growth duration increased from 4 to 17 d as compared with the control.

We found IET5656, IET6314,

MTU5293, and CN540 of appropriate duration for double-cropped lowlands, Pankaj, PLA1100, and NC492 can be single-cropped. MTU5293 is a brown planthopper-tolerant variety. □

Pest Control and Management DISEASES

Polyethylene mulching to control sheath rot (ShR)

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We found that 7 d of mulching with transparent polyethylene sheets killed *Sclerotium oryzae*, which causes ShR, and increased rice yield.

In May 1980-83 at RRI, 3- × 1-m plots of wet soil with 80-90% of moisture

Effect of polyethylene mulching on ShR infestation, number of culms, disease severity index, and yield, Kalashah Kaku, Pakistan.

	Nonmulched			Mulched		
	1980 (IR6)	1982 (Jhona)	1983 (Jhona)	1980 (IR6)	1982 (Jhona)	1983 (Jhona)
No. of culms/hill	21	12	9	21	11	10
Disease severity index	2	1	1	1	1	1
Yield (t/ha) after 7-d mulching	3.6	3.8	1.4	4.4	3.9	1.7
Yield difference after mulching (t/ha)				0.8 or 22.8%	0.2 or 7.5%	0.4 or 23%

holding capacity and pH 7.2 were covered with 400-µm-thick transparent polyethylene sheets. After 7 d, the plastic

mulch was removed, and IR6 was transplanted in 1980 and Jhona in 1982 and 1983. The experiment was in a ran-

domized block with four replications. A control plot was maintained without polyethylene mulch. The crops received normal management and rice was harvested after 5 mo.

Mulching eliminated the natural pop-

ulation of 11 sclerotia/g soil. Loss of sclerotia viability corresponded with an increase in soil temperature from 36°C (nonmulched) to 48°C (mulched) at the 5-cm depth, and from 32°C (nonmulched) to 38°C (mulched) at 20-cm depth.

Plastic mulching increased rice yield 23% over the control (see table). There was no significant difference in the number of culms and in disease severity index. □

Phage sensitivity and lysotype distribution of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzicola*

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Bacteriophages (phages) of plant pathogens are useful tools for detecting bacteria and differentiating them into strains based on sensitivity to lysis of the phage. Phage-typing of tropical *X.c. pv. oryzicola*, the bacterial leaf streak (BLS) pathogen, has identified various natural lysotypes. Differences in phage-host interaction and distribution were also reported. We studied changes in the phage population of *X.c. pv. oryzicola*.

The sensitivity of 44 isolates to 10 phages collected at IRRI was determined by a spot test. One ml of the test bacterial suspension, obtained from a 48-h culture, was mixed with 10 ml of PSA and aseptically seeded in petri plates. Phage suspensions were independently spotted on the seeded medium with a pipette. After 24 h, positive and negative reactions were recorded.

Based on phage sensitivity, the isolates

Lysotypes of *X. c. pv. oryzicola* differentiated by phage reaction, IRRI.

Lysotype	Bacteriophage reaction ^a										Host bacterial isolate
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	
A	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	BLS1, BLS126
B	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	BLS3, BLS119, BLS125
C	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	BLS56, BLS101, BLS128
D	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	BLS22
E	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	BLS124
F	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	BLS79
G	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	-	+	+	BLS53
H	+	-	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	BLS94, BLS95
I	-	-	+	-	+	+	+	+	+	-	BLS28
J	+	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	BLS30
K	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	+	+	+	BLS48
L	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	+	-	-	BLSM
M	+	+	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	BLS54, BLS103
N	+	+	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	BLS69
O	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	+	+	BLS92
P	-	-	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	BLS2, BLS58, BLS64, BLS68, BLS66, BLS81, BLS86, BLS88, BLS93, BLS96, BLS99, BLS102, BLS109, BLS120, BLS123, BLS127
Q	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	BLS17, BLS78
R	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	BLS37, BLS45, BLS93A, BLS51

^a + = sensitive, - = resistant.

of *X.c. pv. oryzicola* were differentiated into 18 lysotypes (see table). Only BLS37, BLS45, BLS93A, and BLS51 isolates were resistant to the phages. They

were collected in Isabela, Nueva Ecija, IRRI, and Camarines Sur. Our findings differ from those reported for the Philippines in the 1960s. □

Assessment of virulence of the bacterial blight (BB) pathogen by infectivity titration

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Graded doses of inoculum were applied to compatible varieties to assess the virulence of strains within a race group of the BB pathogen. This infectivity titration method could help estimate the relative virulence of two or more strains of a BB pathogen by identifying the dose of the strain that would induce BB lesion development on the host, and by explaining the interaction between rice and the BB system.

Table 1. Relationship of induction of positive infection^a and challenge doses of strains in virulence group I of *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* on IR8 at 2 growth stages, IRRI.

Strain	Intersection (a)	Slope (b)	ED ₅₀ ^b	
			Cells ^c (no./ml)	95% fiducial limit
<i>Maximum tillering</i>				
PXO 52	-1.768093	1.180282	5.4 × 10 ⁵ a	4.0 × 10 ⁵ - 7.2 × 10 ⁵
PXO 61	-1.485948	1.123830	5.9 × 10 ⁵ a	2.6 × 10 ⁵ - 1.3 × 10 ⁶
PXO 80	-1.034755	1.143749	1.9 × 10 ⁵ b	4.5 × 10 ⁴ - 7.5 × 10 ⁵
PXO 84	-1.448995	1.175264	3.1 × 10 ⁵ ab	1.0 × 10 ⁵ - 9.4 × 10 ⁵
PXO 85	-0.863743	1.002507	7.1 × 10 ⁵ a	5.2 × 10 ⁵ - 9.6 × 10 ⁵
<i>Flowering</i>				
PXO 52	-0.694496	1.030680	3.3 × 10 ⁵ a	5.3 × 10 ⁴ - 2.3 × 10 ⁶
PXO 61	-0.589263	1.011782	3.3 × 10 ⁵ a	1.0 × 10 ⁵ - 1.2 × 10 ⁶
PXO 80	0.490349	0.855707	1.9 × 10 ⁵ a	3.6 × 10 ⁴ - 9.1 × 10 ⁵
PXO 84	-0.195718	1.013959	1.3 × 10 ⁵ a	3.3 × 10 ⁴ - 4.7 × 10 ⁵
PXO 85	-0.853099	1.029445	4.8 × 10 ⁵ a	1.7 × 10 ⁵ - 1.5 × 10 ⁶

^a Scored at 14 d after inoculation. ^b Based on bacterial cell number in the inoculum suspension. ^c Separation of ED₅₀s at the same stage by Duncan's multiple range test at 5% level.